

MARKETING ETHICS LEADERSHIP FOR FUTURE SLOW FOOD TOURISM IN AGING SOCIETY

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Abstract:

The high rate of competition in globalized capital markets has led to climate change and deteriorating environmental sustainability. Meanwhile, the emergence of covid-19 has made older consumers more concerned about their health and food safety. And slow food tourism as a lifestyle promotes people's physical and mental health and happiness from slow food tourism meals, while also improving local economic income, promoting the preservation and transmission of local traditional culture, and promoting sustainable local economic development. On the other hand, the marketing approach and marketing ethics of slow food tourism can also enhance consumers' sense of social responsibility and promote human concern for sustainable development issues in the world.

Keywords: marketing ethics; future leadership; slow food tourism

INTRODUCTION

Aging societies are one of the major trends in the world, stemming from advances in medicine that have extended the life span of people. Human life expectancy has increased considerably, however, the fundamental question of aging societies is not longevity, but "how will they live?" (Cutler et al., 1990; Michacheles, 2008; Fusté-Forné, P Ginés-Ariza, and E Noguer-Juncà, 2021). In the last few years, the growing interest in gastronomic tourism in many places in Europe and abroad, and the increasing interest of tourists in tourism products based on the discovery of nature, local culture and traditions, suggest that this type of tourism is an important part of the future tourism market (Demir, 2020).

According to related reports, "local production" is the new food trend, which encompasses a tourism marketing ethic that promotes local economic development while preserving the local environment and sustainable resources, and is a growing niche market (Painter 2007; Fataron, 2021). Local foods are in demand not only in the tourism sector, but also in agricultural markets and natural food retailers, as well as in traditional supermarkets and institutions such as schools and hospitals (Nakamoto, Halloran, Yanagida and Leung 1989; Fusté-Forné and Jamal, 2020). However, most local foods are sold not through traditional retail outlets but through other means. For example, farmers sell directly at farmers' markets, farm stands, or community-supported cooperatives. As a result, a form of tourism known as "slow food tourism" is becoming increasingly popular, driven and guided by businesses, attracting visitors from around the world to participate in "eat local" activities. Slow food tourism is so popular and has such a cult following around the world that the area dedicated to it was the most visited at the 2015 World Fair in Milan, Italy. Slow food tourism means that the short delivery of food reduces the environmental damage caused by transportation (Nakamoto, Halloran, Yanagida and Leung 1989; Demir, 2020). In addition, farmers can use chemical-free organic farming

methods that help minimize environmental pollution and may benefit the health of older tourists (Diamond and Barham 2011 ;). Therefore, slow food tourism is also known as one of the suitable activities for older tourists (FAAN, 2010; Udovychenko, 2021).

LITERATURE REVIEW

SlowFood Tourism

In the literature, the term food tourism is often used interchangeably with the terms culinary, gourmet, food, gourmand and food tourism (Peesapati, 2020). Some frequently cited authors, Hall and Sharples, define it as a trip to a gastronomic region, including leisure or entertainment, which includes visits to primary and secondary food producers, food festivals, food fairs, events, farmers' markets, culinary shows, and other food-related tourism activities. According to the WTO, it provides the following broader definition culinary tourism is defined as food-related tourism activities undertaken by tourists and visitors when planning to travel partly or exclusively for the purpose of tasting food (United Nations World Tourism Organization, 2012). Alternatively, the concept of culinary tourism can be summarized as "culinary tourism is a tourism activity that uses the cuisine of a destination as an attraction for tourists".

The tourism trilogy has three main components: food, accommodation, and transportation, of which but the importance of gastronomy has evolved in recent years and is no longer just a biological necessity (Vander Valduga, and Gimenesminasse, 2021). One of the reasons for this is the new awareness of nutrition as an indicator of quality of life, so consumers strive for a healthy diet and the use of modern, so-called organic food." The emergence of the "slow food tourism" craze and the shift in culinary techniques in art and design has also had their influence. So-called "slow food" is not just "anti-fast food"; it is more concerned with the global consistency of flavors in mass production models, the disappearance of traditional ingredients and dishes, and the values of fast-food style living. Slow Food advocates believe in eating slowly, taking the time to enjoy a meal carefully, wholeheartedly and with all the senses, and understanding and supporting the efforts and traditions behind the meal. Slow food's focus on the organic ingredients of traditional cuisine and the traditional folklore associated with it has had an unimaginable impact on food culture (Fataron, 2021). Slow food tourism can be referred to as "tourism activities for the purpose of tasting traditional food". Moreover, tourists seek to immerse themselves in the local culture and enrich their impressions of the destination they visit through exposure to specific foods and beverages and related traditions and techniques (Valduga, Henriqueta, Garcia and Minasse, 2020). Needless to say, this type of tourism received a particular boost after the World Gastronomic Congress organized by the World Tourism Organization (WTO) in Larnaca in 2000 and the recognition of the Mediterranean diet as an intangible cultural heritage of humanity. In 2010, the Mediterranean diet was recognized as an intangible cultural heritage of humanity and in some countries, such as France and Italy, this food has gained the status of a national treasure.

Marketing Ethics

An often used definition of marketing is: "Marketing is the human activity of satisfying needs and desires through a process of exchange" (Kotler and Turner, 1981; Pozo and Tachizawa, 2018). The most striking feature of this definition is that it is almost entirely utilitarian. This characteristic is typical of marketing, whose central theme since its original definition has been the satisfaction of consumer needs. And nowadays, one would tend to believe that satisfying consumer needs is the ultimate goal of marketing, while the morality of the methods used in its process is still highly debatable (Landler, 1991; Anwar and El-Bassiouny, 2020).

In reality, important activities of marketers have the potential to raise ethical issues (Hise and McGinnis, 1975; Anwar and El-Bassiouny, 2020). Among them, advertising management is probably the most effective factor in marketing strategy. So at this point, advertising is undoubtedly the most important of all marketing functions. There is no doubt that advertising is the most regulated. However, despite being regulated, the act of advertising has given rise to many controversies (Wright and Merters, 1974; Eagle et al., 2020). For example, the number of advertisements that use classical conditioning to transfer the emotional burden initially attributed to the endorser to the advantages of their product. A famous actor or a reputable athlete endorses a product with little intrinsic value, but still generates a certain amount of fan purchase for the product (Galbraith, 1991; Eagle et al., 2020). Or market research, although the research function may appear more objective in principle, raises certain questions about its ethics. Tybout and Zaltman (1974) argue that the use (and often misuse) of surveys is an invasion of consumer privacy (Ahadiat et al., 2021). Ferrell and Skinner (1988), on the other hand, argue that. Condemned the practice of telemarketing under the guise of surveys (Ahadiat et al., 2021).

In addition, among all product attributes, the price of a product represents an objective criterion that should allow consumers to be able to infer the ratio of quality to price. While the law on pricing is very clear on this issue, this does not prevent certain business practices from misrepresenting the price of a product. Retailers will use advertised price reductions of X% to distort consumers' perception of the price of a product, when in fact such reductions are based on the normal price of the product. So there exist situations where retailers use false reference prices in order to advertise that a product is selling (Nason and Della Bitta, 1983; Athwal, 2019). Gwinner et al. (1977) and Laczniak and Murphy mention that some companies have introduced products with a limited life span in order to be able to benefit from premature repurchases benefit from premature repurchases. The same happens with products that, although not sold through false advertising, fail to meet the needs and expectations of consumers. For example, treated wood, whose 40-year guarantee is valid only under certain specific conditions, nevertheless serves to reassure consumers (Pépin, 1990; Athwal, 2019).

Since marketing is largely a product of the market economy, we cannot impose a strict ethical code. Companies that are more dynamic in their marketing will adopt operating rules that are designed to govern their marketing practices (Pengyi and Demin, 2019). For example, in recent years a phenomenon has emerged that links the environment and consumption.

Consumers are not only concerned about the final product, but also about the marketing process. Many companies are therefore influenced by consumers who are concerned not only with the quality of finished products, but also with the way those finished products are produced and marketed. The challenge of over-packaging Product packaging has long been considered one of the pillars of product marketing. Cosmetics, for example, are a concrete manifestation of this phenomenon (Brown, 1989; Javalgi and Russell, 2018; He and Harris, 2020).

In sum, there are many reasons to believe that marketing approaches will move closer and closer to the ethical ideal level, a position supported by the increasing number of boycotts and protests organized by individual consumers and activists (Garrett, 1987; Smith, 1987 ; Garrett et al., 1989; McCune, 1990; He and Harris, 2020).

Aging Society

According to World Population Prospects: 2019 Revision, the global population aged 65 and older is growing faster than younger age groups, with 1 in 6 people worldwide aged 65 or older (16%) by 2050, compared to 11 (9%) in 2019; and 1 in 4 people in Europe and North America aged 65 or In 2018, for the first time in history, the global population aged 65 or older exceeded the number of people under 5 years old. Furthermore, the population aged 80 or older is projected to triple, from 143 million in 2019 to 426 million in 2050 (Castiglioni et al., 2020). Therefore, it becomes extremely urgent and important to plan sensibly for the future lifestyle of old age.

OBJECTIVES AND METHODOLOGY

The qualitative research method used in this paper, 79 small-scale questionnaires were distributed to designated consumers (aged 55 years or older) through the online questionnaire platform "Questionnaire Star", with a 100% return rate. Therefore, this study used these 79 questionnaires to gain a preliminary understanding of older consumers' perceptions and purchase intentions of slow food tourism; and found expert interview transcripts and relevant literature to summarize the concept, current development status, and marketing ethics of slow food tourism, with a view to providing a little reference for a healthy lifestyle in an aging society in the future.

CURRENT SITUATION

Slow food tourism development

Slow Food Tours is an organization that promotes local food and traditional cooking. It was founded in Italy in 1986 by Carlo Petrini and has since taken the world by storm. As an alternative to fast food, it strives to preserve traditional and local cuisine and encourages the cultivation of plants, seeds and livestock unique to local ecosystems, and it promotes local small businesses and sustainable development. It also focuses on food quality rather than quantity (Alvarez and Campo, 2014). In the process, it opposes overproduction and food waste,

prompting local small farmers and food producers to be protected at the same time (Avraham, 2015).

The slow food movement values artisanal, quality local foods that provide a rich aesthetic experience and promote a sense of place and terroir. This terminology encapsulates the idea that "the particular interplay of geographic, historical, and human factors gives food a special flavor that cannot be reproduced elsewhere" (Musgrave, 2009). It is associated with a happy human society that contributes to happiness and well-being (Dunlap, 2012; Hall and Sharples, 2003), and celebrates cultural and culinary heritage (Miele and Murdoch, 2002).

Slow food tourism functions in various forms of slow experiences that provide residents and visitors (urban and rural) with bioregional food experiences that are friendly and rooted in the local "terroir." For example, slow food tourism can take place in home stay programs, small-scale ecotourism and farm visits, farmers' markets, slow food tourism experiences, and small-scale food businesses. In these local, personalized spaces, small-scale producers, accommodation hosts, and food service providers work with consumers to create enjoyable experiences for consumers, experience ethnic and cultural diversity, and achieve economies of supply and substitution (Berno and Fuste´-Forne´, 2019; Stone et al., 2018). For example, niche specialties like cheese produced by small rural producers (Fuste´-Forne´, 2015) provide such a slow, holistic gastronomic opportunity to enjoy cheese tasting, explore rural landscapes, and contribute to sustainable livelihoods and social well-being. It brings visitors and residents together as active rather than passive consumers, engaging in socialization, dialogue, storytelling, and cultural exchange with local suppliers (Lappe´, 1991). They can make informed choices about what they want to eat, understand where it comes from, how it is grown and distributed how it is used, and how it affects ecological health and our health. Grounded in this relational ethic, these behaviors can promote environmental stewardship and civic democracy (Clancy, 2017 ; Jamal, 2019). As Wendell Berry states, "eating is an agricultural act," and the industrial eater is a passive, uncritical eater who no longer knows the connections between food, agriculture, and land. And the connection between land (Berry, 1992). In contrast, the slow food tourist recognizes the need to move away from unsustainable industrial agriculture and its neoliberal capitalist ethic to a healthier, more conscious way of life and concern for sustaining the ecosystems and spaces of the earth's inhabitants.

Slow food tourism market

Over time, new spaces for slow tourism experiences have emerged, such as markets and slow food-themed festivals. Festivals that incorporate a slow food theme. The Jokkmokk winter market in Swedish Lapland has been around for over 400 years, but in 2011, "slow tourism" became an official theme and restaurants were encouraged to meet the Slowfood Sa´pmi organization's criteria of "pleasant, ecological and fair (Barre and Brouder, 2013) ". Laing and Frost (2010) describe a variety of events with Slowfood as an overarching theme. Such as the Taste of Slow Food festival in Melbourne, Australia, and the Slow Food Nation and Slow Food Home festivals in San Francisco, USA. Slow Food Nation Festival in San Francisco, United States, and the Slow Food Movement's Salone Del Gastronomia in Turin, Italy. The rural food festival Salone Del Gusto has a more political and anti-globalization agenda, including a bureau

that supports small food producers and local food. Supporting small food producers and local food varieties, biodiversity conservation, and educating visitors about the importance of traditional knowledge and food safety (Siniscalchi, 2013).

In addition, through food tourism, tourists have the opportunity to demonstrate their social responsibility in their travels and to contribute to the improvement of the living standards of local communities through conscious consumption of local food products. The research community has long documented the occurrence of this phenomenon in the research community: the LOHAS (Lifestyle of Health and Sustainability) of tourists, which is not only a way of travelling, but a way of life as a whole. Based on the desire for health and equity, aimed at sustainable development of gastronomic tourism. In response, the tourism industry has also integrated CSR practices into its core business. According to the U.S. Travel Association Tourism Association, Americans are choosing gastronomic vacations more than ever before, accounting for 19% of all American travel (UNWTO, 2012). For example, culinary cruises and cooking classes on classic food tours in Italy, France and Spain have gained popularity. Some of the countries with developed food tourism are some of the largest immigrant markets, such as the United States, Australia, New Zealand, and Canada some developed countries have large immigrant markets and so make great efforts to promote their traditional or avant-garde cuisine through special marketing strategies. Food tourism is becoming one of the most promising trends in tourism in the tourism industry (Laudan, 2004).

Slow food tourism ethics

As Fullagar and others have explained, the ethic of "slow" is reflected in the qualities of rhythm, pace, cadence, and speed that result from the sensory and emotional relationship between the traveler and the world. It is reflected in a number of social movements, including the slow food and slow city movements, slow tourism, and the slow movement (Dickinson et al., 2011). The Slow Food movement was started by Carlo Petrini in 1986 as a response to a campaign for moral justice at a McDonald's fast food restaurant in Rome. The principles of the Slow Food movement are "good, clean and fair", promoting "local ingredients, traditional recipes and taking the time to source, prepare and enjoy food" ((Dickinson and Lumsdon, 2010), and upholding environmental health, resisting the damage to human health caused by fast food and fast lifestyles, and ensuring fair labor and work practices (Andrews, 2008). The Slow Food Manifesto also calls for "benign globalization." Promoting local entrepreneurs and family businesses to reduce the pressure of environmental pollution through local artisanal food practices (Sidali et al., 2015). As Frost and Laing (2013) describe, in addition to fostering foodie taste and enjoyment, the movement hopes to build social capital through strong community connections as well as provide opportunities for people to perceive this as a strong political statement and respond to globalization.

LEADERSHIP FOR FUTURE

Product guarantee

Food and gastronomy account for 40% of world tourism spending (Europa Press, 2019). For example, in Spain, 15% of tourists are influenced by food and gastronomy. Their budget is 20% higher than that of the average tourist. (KPMG, 2019). The practice of tasting, eating, sharing, and learning about food often involves individuals or families interacting with local businesses, many of which have deep roots in cultural heritage, intergenerational knowledge, and livelihoods on the land, an advantage that can greatly enhance the consumer's food experience (Stone et al., 2018). At the same time, tourism, slow food tourism, and food safety are closely related, and when combined, they can positively impact the performance and image of a destination to the benefit of visitors and locals alike. Food tourism in destinations continues to attract an increasing number of visitors. Eight out of ten visitors are influenced by culinary attractions when choosing a destination.

Ingredients, preparation methods and packaging are the three main issues related to availability and food safety, as a high level of quality is required for the sustainable development of food tourism (Vitic and Ringer, 2007), especially when serving older tourists, which means that slow food tourism must meet the safety requirements of tourism if it is to be a real development factor. The tourism industry can work with local communities to open up a tourism program that incorporates gastronomy and makes local cuisine a strong competitive force. The local tourism program should offer a product that can interest the modern tourist in new trends, able to care and take care of his health (Fullagar et al., 2012). The second benefit is mainly the contribution to the local food system, obtaining better living conditions and a higher standard of living for the local communities in which they live (Platania, 2013). Gastronomic tourism creates excellent opportunities for a better integration of local communities in tourism and should be committed to a smooth tourism development by improving the quality of services and at the same time diversifying the tourism portfolio of the destination, which will reduce the seasonality of tourist flows.

In recent years, the tourism industry in underdeveloped countries is constantly looking for new ways to promote a new image, with new competitive advantages, in order to shed the current image of a cheap tourist destination. Due to the great potential of the region in the field of food tourism, it offers an excellent opportunity to achieve this goal. Therefore the competitiveness of food tourism needs to be taken into account in the promotion of the destination, while food and services for older tourists need to achieve improved service quality and food safety (Siniscalchi, 2013).

Marketing design

Tourism is one of the largest industries in the world and the fastest growing industry in the market (Cooper and Hall, 2008). Worldwide, tourism is the second largest revenue-generating industry after the oil industry (Rathore, 2012) and can promote understanding of foreign places, human interaction, empathy and tolerance (Salazar, 2006). Thus, we believe that food, especially culinary activities, can be a driver of tourism, and even more effective when used as

an educational tool. Subtle strategies (such as food tasting experiences) are effective marketing tools due to the fact that the emotional component (feelings and emotions) is key to tourists' choice of vacation destination (Alvarez and Campo, 2014).

An aggressive marketing and promotional strategy (outdoor and online marketing campaigns) is not always a solution. Non-promotional communication may be more powerful than more explicit promotion (Connell, 2013). When people have a better understanding of the true nature of a destination (history, traditions, context, etc.), they are more likely to visit because they are less susceptible to distortions, exaggerations, and unbalanced claims (Sraphin, 2014). Kirillova, Fu, Lehto, and Cai (2014) explain that what tourists perceive as aesthetically pleasing or beautiful (the environment, the product or service, tourism experience) contribute to their decision to visit the same destination and to show loyalty to that destination in the long term. Kirillova et al. (2014) also argue that knowledge and objectivity about the environment affects appreciation (Sraphin, 2012). Their analysis implies that objective knowledge and exposure to a more balanced narrative affects the way potential visitors choose a destination, not only on a cognitive/rational basis, but also on an emotional basis (Krippendorf, 1987). They found that when consumers browse in-store, they are in physical proximity to the product. Therefore, this proximity leads to an impulse to buy (Beatty and Ferrell, 1998). In this regard, slow food tourism can be used as an effective marketing tool that greatly increases the probability of customer purchase if the person selling the food provides information about where it comes from, when it is usually served, and what it is made from (Walters and Mair, 2012). Slow food tourism as part of an organized activity (culinary event) can maximize the positive impact of food as a tourism tool and can be an excellent opportunity to introduce visitors to other aspects of the destination.

Integrated with senior tourism

As slow food tourism is particularly popular in developing countries, we can assume that this rather traditional habit can be used as a low-cost and sustainable tourism tool. Combining the retailing of local cuisine with tourism services and cultural programs (e.g., rural tourism, incentive tourism or ecotourism) can contribute to the economic development of a region. For example, rural accommodation providers, restaurants, bike rentals, cultural program organizers, bakers, fishermen and other local producers can collaborate and join together in a trademark system. Serving consumers together with standard, high-quality design and common organization is more likely to enhance the consumer experience.

Governments should create an enabling environment that promotes multi-stakeholder collaboration to drive resource efficiency. Given the cross-cutting nature of tourism, all SDGs can be addressed by governments working closely with industry, civil society, and academia (Wise, 2019). Tourism governance mechanisms need to include certification schemes based on specific and measurable goals and targets. Sustainable marketing should aim to reduce environmental and social impacts, educate tourists and locals, reduce seasonality, and attract the tourists we really need (Bowen and Morosan, 2018).

An inclusive tourism sector not only brings benefits to its direct beneficiaries, but also improves competitiveness and quality. Better distribution of tourism flows brings new customers and more revenue (Andrews, 2008). First we think out of the box and understand that different groups of tourists will have different needs and that effective and user-friendly communication is key in this process (Rathore, 2012). For elderly tourists with mobility problems and in good physical condition, we need to target our marketing platform and marketing approach from the beginning, and we need to assess what their individual accessibility requirements are in the setting of the tour program to ensure a comfortable tour experience (Cooper and Hall, 2008).

Social responsibility

Among the daunting global environmental challenges, including population growth and the climate crisis, increased vulnerability due to climate change (Dogru et al., 2019). Hall (2006) was early to make the connection between the slow food movement and slow tourism. As a tourist who stays longer in a place, he deliberately seeks to buy local products, thus ensuring that money stays at the destination. One should travel only locally, he thought, to minimize "food miles". And support the economic benefits of local food production and consumption. Barre and Brouder (2013), observing slow tourism in the Arctic, found that slow food tourism can foster food security by promoting local well-being, protecting biodiversity, and caring for the land (Bertella and Vidmar, 2019). Due to the limited transportation of food, reduced emissions and much less harm to the local ecosystem, while providing more and better employment opportunities for local people (Fuste´-Forne´, 2019), promoting the acquisition of new knowledge and skills (Lenzen et al., 2018), promoting social contact between people in urban and rural areas, having more cooperation opportunities to bring new capital into the local economy and increase the income of small producers, thus improving their quality of life (Shiva, 2000; Wise, 2019).

RESEARCH FINDINGS

The 79 questionnaires collected, about half of the respondents indicated that they had heard of and were interested in slow food tourism, and more than half believed that slow food tourism could contribute to local economic development, environmental protection and the spread of traditional culture.

More than half of the respondents said they had learned about slow food tourism through TV and radio, social media platforms, newspapers and magazines, or word of mouth; among them, food safety, cooking methods and ingredients were the most important, followed by local culture, background culture and price; more than half of the respondents said they preferred to travel freely with relatives and friends, while only a very small number of respondents chose to travel with a group or alone. This shows that the current recognition and popularity of slow food tourism is high.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 1: Established based on research by Euronews, Lewis and O'Connor (2020)

The combined pressures of today's aging world and the outbreak of epidemics are driving concerns about the external environment and one's own health. Because Slow Food Tourism promotes a healthy, slow-paced and environmentally friendly lifestyle, it is likely to become the preferred mode of travel for older consumers in the future. At the same time, the marketing ethics of slow food tourism will be transformed into a good model for food safety, environmental protection, and sustainable development of tourism destinations, making the concept of slow food tourism a leading force for healthy living (Euronews, Lewis and O'Connor, 2020).

The impact of Covid-19 on the global economy may be unprecedented since the Great Depression of the 1930s (Euronews, 2020). Thus, the Covid-19 pandemic may represent one of the most important environmental changes in modern marketing history, and it may have a profound impact on corporate social responsibility (CSR), marketing ethics, and basic marketing concepts. Previous marketers were overly focused on the physical characteristics of their products and myopically ignored the underlying needs of their customers; this pandemic is more like a tunnel vision of pandemic-driven consumer panic buying and hoarding (Lewis, 2020), such as during a pandemic. The potential areas of consumer focus consumption are health and wellness, such as vitamin supplements, painkillers, and fever reducers, which are directly related to the new covid-19 virus. The more interesting question is the extent to which consumers will shift to more health and wellness product consumption in the long run. Will consumers generally become more health-conscious in their product choices? Given the strong evidence that healthy and fit people are less likely to suffer from serious viruses, we expect a strong shift toward health and wellness consumption, not only in food and nutrition but also in health and wellness programs, and even a fundamental shift toward more responsible and pro-social consumption (O'Connor, 2020).

Slow food tourism has great potential to support healthy ecosystems, cultural heritage, and local livelihoods. And opposes hegemonic and industrial agriculture, which makes it a powerful micro-trend for local recovery and climate crisis action. The Slow Food Ethic

promotes gender equality, sustainable livelihoods and well-being through the "benign globalization" promoted by the Slow Food movement. Slow food tourism also promotes reflection on the nature and ethics of what we eat, it makes co-production and co-consumption of food a pleasurable experience, and cares for the land and its human and non-human inhabitants through diverse, pluralistic, relational and contextualized practices for a sustainable planet ((Lappe, 1991; Bertella and Vidmar, 2019).

Slow food focuses on the organic ingredients of traditional cuisine and the traditional folk culture associated with it. Slow Food tourism is practice-oriented and promotes civil society, democracy, and active participants in food behavior and policy action. It is an important advocate for addressing key 21st century planetary issues and climate (Swain et al., 2018). The contribution of slow food tourism to globalization is the slow process of de-growth and supply by supporting small-scale producers and alternative economies, as well as recycling local resources.

Slow food tourism helps to promote food security and contributes to human and environmental health. A community-based effort that promotes sociability, learning, celebration, and sharing of cultural traditions (Wise, 2019). As a supplier, implementing a slow food tourism program also has many benefits that contribute to the well-being of customers, workers, and the communities in which they are located; it attracts a new customer base and promotes sustainable consumption patterns; enhances the company's credibility, makes employees proud of their work, helps modify their supply chain, and contributes to the sustainability of local communities.

CONCLUSION

Tourism destinations around the world are facing existential threats from climate change and degradation of environmental sustainability. Climate change and the degradation of environmental sustainability are caused by the high rate of competition in a globalized capital market. Coupled with the outbreak in 2020, doctors advised people to go out less to ensure the speed of the outbreak, a move that plunged the global tourism economy into crisis (Euronews, 2020), but with the concerted efforts of countries around the world, the outbreak has begun to gradually die down and the next major task is to recover the economy.

Meanwhile, with the advent of an aging society, the pursuit of a healthy lifestyle has become more urgent, making consumers more concerned about their health and food safety. Slow food tourism is emerging as an important micro-trend of the slow food movement, which can not only breathe new life into tourism activities, but also slow down the frenzied consumer society. Slow food is becoming a global phenomenon, not only in major cities but actually on a much larger scale, involving a large number of consumers, both young and non-young. And more and more people are dining out and tending to choose specialty dishes. Consumers of slow food tourism say, "By enjoying a slow food tourism meal, you not only compensate for the physical need for energy requirements, but also experience a contribution to the sustainability of the region" (Yeoman and McMahon-Beatte, 2016).

Apparently, based on the content of the literature and the respondents' responses, we can understand that slow food tourism not only generates health benefits for the purchasers, but also promotes the economic development of the destination, advances the dissemination and preservation of the local traditional food culture, and most importantly, protects the local environment and promotes the recycling of local ecological resources.

Slow food tourism advocates tourists to taste local traditional food at the destination, support local produce, and experience the local people and traditional culture behind the food, which not only reduces the transportation of food on the road and ensures freshness, but also reduces environmental pollution from the transportation process. Slow food tourism then drives local economic development, encourages local residents to start businesses and learn new skills, increases opportunities to interact with the outside world, advances the realization of the local workforce, and improves local living conditions.

The marketing ethic of slow food tourism also has the potential to influence the future sustainability and progress of society. Slow food tourism encourages tourists to strengthen their own sense of social responsibility, actively participate in actions to protect the ecological environment of the destination and reduce pollutant emissions, promote local economic development while satisfying their own food needs, and start small with the ultimate ideal of solving the sustainability problems of the human world.

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